

Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for The Quantitative Estimation of Inosine Pranobex in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The objective of the present study was to develop a novel RP-HPLC method for Inosine Pranobex using a unique mobile phase ratio for the first time and validate a simple, rapid, precise, and accurate reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the estimation of Inosine Pranobex in bulk drug and tablet dosage form, followed by forced degradation studies to assess the stability-indicating nature of the method. **Methodology:** Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Shimadzu C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm × 5 μm) using a mobile phase consisting of water: acetonitrile: methanol in the ratio of 80:10:10 %v/v/v. The flow rate was maintained at 0.7 ml/min, and detection was carried out at 259 nm using a UV detector. **Results:** The method exhibited good linearity in the concentration range of 20–100 μg/ml, with correlation coefficient (R^2 0.9999) values meeting ICH acceptance criteria. System suitability testing showed peak asymmetry factors of < 1.0 and theoretical plate numbers greater than 2000, indicating efficient chromatographic performance. The % RSD for precision studies was found to be less than 2.0 %, confirming method reproducibility. Forced degradation results demonstrated that there was no significant interference from degradation products at the retention time of the analyte, confirming the stability-indicating property of the method. **Conclusion:** The developed RP-HPLC method is simple, precise, accurate, and robust, and can be successfully applied for routine quantitative estimation of Inosine Pranobex in bulk and tablet dosage forms, as well as for stability assessment under forced degradation conditions.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, validation, forced degradation, ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Inosine pranobex, also known by several synonyms such as inosine acedoben dimepranol (International Nonproprietary Name, INN), methisoprinol, inosiplex, and Isoprinosine, is a synthetic antiviral and immunomodulatory agent widely used in clinical therapeutics. It is a fixed-dose combination of inosine and dimepranol acedoben a salt compound formed from acetamidobenzoic acid and dimethylamino isopropanol in a precise stoichiometric ratio of 1:3^[1-3]. This unique combination enhances the overall pharmacological activity of the drug, allowing it to exert dual antiviral and immunostimulant effects.^[4-6] Inosine pranobex has gained significant clinical relevance, especially in European countries, where it

is commonly prescribed for the management of acute viral infections, including but not limited to the common cold, herpes simplex virus infections, and human papillomavirus-related conditions.^[7] The drug functions by modulating the host immune response, facilitating lymphocyte proliferation, stimulating the production of cytokines such as interferons, and enhancing natural killer (NK) cell activity, which collectively contribute to faster clearance of viral pathogens. Its mechanism of action differs from conventional antiviral agents, as inosine pranobex does not act by directly inhibiting viral replication but rather by boosting the body's innate and adaptive immune responses.^[8-9] Chemically, inosine pranobex consists of 4-acetamidobenzoic acid, inosine (9-[(2R,3R,4S,5R)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)]

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oxolan-2-yl]-1H-purin-6-one), and 1-(dimethylamino) propan-2-ol, [10-11] as illustrated in Figure 1. This molecular complexity underlines its multifaceted pharmacodynamics and therapeutic potential, making it an important candidate for antiviral drug development and clinical application.

FIGURE 1: Chemical structure of Inosine Pranobex

Accurate and reliable analytical methods are essential for the quality control and stability assessment of pharmaceutical compounds. Reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) has emerged as a preferred technique due to its inherent advantages. RP-HPLC is an economical, simple, and highly precise analytical method capable of separating complex mixtures efficiently. It offers rapid analysis with short run times, making it ideal for routine quality control. Furthermore, RP-HPLC methods are well-suited for detecting and quantifying degradation products, thereby enabling comprehensive stability-indicating studies. These attributes make RP-HPLC a valuable tool in the development and validation of methods for pharmaceutical formulations such as inosine pranobex.

Drug profile: [13]

Drug Name: Inosine Pranobex

Chemical Name: 4-acetamidobenzoic acid 9-[(2R,3R,4S,5R)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)oxolan-2-yl]-1H-purin-6-one, 1-(dimethyl amino) propan-2-ol (Inosine Pranobex)

Molecular Formula: C₅₂H₇₈N₁₀O₁₇

Molecular Weight: 1,115.23 g/mol

Structure: Purine nucleoside derivative with immunomodulatory properties

Mechanism of Action:

- Enhances T-cell function and increases lymphocyte proliferation.
- Stimulates natural killer (NK) cells and cytokine production.
- Exhibits antiviral activity by boosting host immune response.

Therapeutic Uses:

- Treatment of viral infections such as herpes simplex, subacute sclerosing panencephalitis (SSPE), and influenza.
- Immunomodulatory agent in certain chronic infections.

Dosage Form: Tablets, oral solution

Pharmacokinetics:

- Absorption: Rapid oral absorption
- Distribution: Widely distributed in tissues
- Metabolism: Partially metabolized in liver
- Excretion: Primarily renal
- **Adverse Effects:**
 - Gastrointestinal disturbances (nausea, vomiting)
 - Headache, dizziness
 - Rare: hypersensitivity reactions

Storage: Store in a cool, dry place, protected from light.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Instrumentation:

Shimadzu HPLC system (Shimadzu C₁₈ 4.5 × 250mm × 5 μm column, UV-Visible detector, Lab solution software), Shimadzu HPLC system LC-20AD, all weighing was done on electronic balance (Model

Shimadzu AUX- 220), Sonicator was used for sonication of the sample solution, Hot air oven InfraDIGI-250°C.

Materials and chemicals:

A Pure Inosine Pranobex was received from pharmaceutical company in Mumbai, India.

- HPLC grade water
- HPLC grade Acetonitrile
- HPLC grade methanol

A pharmaceutical preparation was purchased from the local pharmacy.

In stability studies used to chemical such as 0.1N H₂SO₄, 0.1N KOH, HPLC grade water, 0.3 % hydrogen peroxide, 10 % sodium bisulfate.

METHOD OPTIMIZATION:

Selection of diluent:

HPLC water, methanol was individually evaluated as mobile phase solvents. Based on their chromatographic performance, a mixture of water: methanol: acetonitrile (80:10:10 % v/v/v) was finalized, providing sharp peak, good resolution and consistent retention time for inosine Pranobex

Selection of wavelength

Inosine Pranobex in diluent (water: acetonitrile: methanol 80:10:10 %v/v/v) was scanned in the range of 200–400 nm. The spectrum has shown 259 nm as a suitable wavelength for the present RP-HPLC method. Inosine Pranobex has shown good absorption at this wavelength.

Optimization of mobile phase

The selected mobile phase i.e. Water, methanol and acetonitrile have been tried in different proportions to get the most optimized peak.

TABLE 1: The different ratios of mobile phase tried and remark on obtained peaks

Sl.NO	MOBILE PHASE	RATIO	FLOW RATE	DILUENT	RT	REMARKS
1	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol	40:30:30 % v/v/v	1ml/min	Methanol	2.025	Peak shape not good low retention time
2		40:30:30 % v/v/v + 0.1 % formic acid	0.7 ml/min	Methanol	4.183	Peak can be splitted
3		60:15:25 % v/v/v	1ml/min	Methanol	1.807	Very low retention and peak shape not good
4		60:15:25 % v/v/v	0.7ml/min	Methanol	2.541	Still peak shape not good
5		80:10:10 % v/v/v	1ml/min	HPLC-grade water	1.906	Peak shape not good and low retention time
6		80:10:10 % v/v/v	0.7ml/min	Mobile phase	2.895	Peak shape was good and excellence satisfactory retention time

Preparation of mobile phase:

Mobile phase was prepared by mixing HPLC grade water, Acetonitrile HPLC grade, Methanol HPLC grade in the ratio of 80:10:10 % v/v/v. The prepared mobile phase was sonicated for 15 mins. And filtered through a 0.22 µm membrane filter to remove the impurities which may interfere with final chromatogram.

Diluent preparation

The mobile phase was used as diluent.

Chromatographic separation

The chromatogram was run for appropriate minutes (10 min) with mobile phase water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 % v/v/v). The detection was carried out at wavelength 259 nm. The chromatogram was stopped after separation was achieved completely. Data related to peaks like area,

height, retention time, etc. were recorded using software.

Chromatographic conditions

TABLE 2: Optimized conditions for estimating Inosine pranobex

PARAMETER	CONDITIONS
Column	C ₁₈
Mobile Phase	water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 % v/v/v)
Flow Rate	0.7 ml/min
Diluent	water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 %v/v/v) same as mobile phase
Detection Wavelength	259 nm
Injection volume	20 µL
Mode	Isocratic
Run time	10 mins

Preparation of standard stock solution

The standard stock solution of Inosine Pranobex was prepared by accurately weighing 100 mg of Inosine Pranobex drug and transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask and added to 10 ml of diluent mixed vigoursly. The above mixture was dissolved and the volume made up the mark with diluent to an obtained concentration of 4000 µgm/ml.

Preparation of working standard solution

From pipetted out 5.0 ml of the above solution 4000 µgm/ml was transferred into 100 ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent to an obtained concentration of 200 µgm/ml.

Quantitative estimation of Marketed Formulation

Preparation of sample solution for assay

Twenty tablets were accurately weighed, crushed, and homogenized into a fine powder. An amount of powder equivalent to 500 mg of Inosine Pranobex was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask. Approximately 30 ml of diluent was added, and the mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution of the active ingredient. The volume was then adjusted to the mark with diluent and the solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper to remove insoluble excipients. From the filtered solution, 2 ml was accurately pipetted into a 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with the diluent; to get concentration 200 µgm/ml Subsequently, 2 ml of this solution was further

diluted to 10 ml with diluent to prepare a final concentration of 40 µgm/ml. This solution was used for routine HPLC analysis.

HPLC Method Validation [12]

System Suitability

The system suitability was performed by injecting a standard solution Inosine pranobex. For two of them, the peak asymmetric were <1 and the theoretical plate number was > 2000, and the % RSD of Inosine Pranobex was less than 2. The result indicates that the system suitability parameter was within the acceptable limit.

Linearity

The linearity for Inosine Pranobex was assessed by analysis of working standard solution in the range of 20-100 µgm/ml and 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of solutions were pipette out from the working standard solution of Inosine Pranobex (200 µgm/ml) and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and makeup with diluent to obtain 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µgm/ml. The linearity for Inosine Pranobex was assessed by analysis of standard solution in the range of 20 - 100 µgm/ml. The correlation coefficient for calibration curve Inosine Pranobex was found to be 0.9999.

Precision

The precision of the developed method has been checked by studying it on six times in same day. A standard solution containing (40 µgm/ml) of Inosine

Pranobex was analysed six times on the % R.S.D was calculated.

Accuracy

40 µgm/ml drug solution was taken in three different flask labels A, B and C. Spiked 50 %, 100 %, and 150 % of the working standard solution in it and diluted up to 10 ml. The area of each solution peak was measured at 259 nm. The amount of Inosine Pranobex was calculated at each level and % recoveries were computed.

LOD and LOQ:

Several approaches for determining the LOD & LOQ are possible depending on whether the procedure is non instrumental or instrumental. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using equation $LOD=3.3 \times \text{Avg. S.D/S}$. and $LOQ= 10 \times \text{Avg. S.D/S}$. where, “Avg. S.D/S is the average of standard deviation of absorbance, and “S” is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness of the proposed method was determined by analysis for 40 µg/ml concentration of Inosine Pranobex sample solution was performed by two analysts and two instruments using the same operational and environmental conditions.

Robustness

For robustness study, the following parameters have been changed one by one and their effects on system suitability were observed.

- i) Change mobile phase composition by ± 1.0 ml of Water and organic solvent.
- ii) Change Wavelength ± 1 nm
- iii) Change flow rate ± 0.1 ml/min.

Change in mobile phase composition: Standard the working solution was injected three times by change in the mobile phase composition by ± 1.0 ml of organic solvent (water: acetonitrile: methanol) (81:9:10 %v/v/v and 78:11:11%v/v/v) of the developed method.

Change in wavelength: Standard the working solution was injected three times by change in the Wavelength by ± 1 nm of a sample (258 nm and 260 nm) of the developed method. Calculate the % RSD of the mean area for change in the method parameter.

Change in flow rate: Standard the working solution was injected three times by change in the flow rate by ± 0.1 ml/min (0.8 ml/min and 0.6 ml/min) of the developed method. Calculate the % RSD of mean area for change in method parameter.

Degradation Studies of Inosine Pranobex: ^[14-17]

Degradation studies of the raw material are crucial for understanding the inherent stability and chemical behaviour of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). These studies help identify degradation pathways and support the development of stability-indicating analytical methods. Reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) is widely used due to its sensitivity and ability to separate degradation products from the parent drug. In this study, Inosine Pranobex raw material was subjected to forced degradation under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, hydrolysis, reduction, thermal, photolytic and UV light conditions. The standard were analyzed using a validated RP-HPLC method to assess degradation profiles and confirm the method's specificity and stability-indicating capability.

Acid degradation

From 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex working standard solution 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask. To this 2 ml of 0.1N H₂SO₄ was added and allowed to stand for 24hrs. then the solution was neutralized by adding 2 ml of 0.1 N KOH and the volume was made up to the mark using diluent (mobile phase) and injected into the HPLC system for chromatographic analysis. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor any changes or new degradation peaks are formed during the stress period.

Base degradation

From 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex working standard solution 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask. To this 2 ml of 0.1N KOH was added and allowed to stand for 24hrs. then the solution was neutralized by adding 2 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ and the

volume was made up to the mark using diluent (mobile phase) and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor the formation of degradation peaks and to assess the rate of degradation.

Hydrolytic degradation

From 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex working standard solution 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Then, 3 ml of HPLC-grade water was added to induce forced degradation, and the mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours. The solution was diluted to volume with the diluent (mobile phase). and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor degradation and evaluate the stability profile of the drug.

Oxidative degradation

From 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex working standard solution 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask. To this 1ml of 0.3% hydrogen peroxide was added and allowed to stand for 24 hrs. then the volume was made up to mark using diluent (mobile phase) and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor the extent of degradation and identify any new degradation peaks.

Reduction degradation

From 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex working standard solution 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Forced degradation was induced by adding 2 ml of 10% sodium bisulfate, and the solution was allowed to stand undisturbed for 24 hours. The volume was then adjusted to the mark with diluent (mobile phase) and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to monitor degradation and evaluate the stability profile of the drug under reductive conditions.

Thermal degradation

The standard inosine pranobex was accurately weighed and subjected to thermal degradation by placing it in an oven maintained at 70°C for 24 hours. From this 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex solution was prepared and 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml

volumetric flask, diluted to volume with the diluent (mobile phase), and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to assess the extent of thermal degradation.

Photolytic degradation

The standard inosine pranobex was weighed and exposed to sunlight for 4 hrs. From this 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex solution was prepared and 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with the diluent (mobile phase). and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to evaluate the photostability of the drug.

UV degradation

The standard inosine pranobex was weighed and exposed to UV light 24 hrs. From this 200 µg/ml inosine pranobex solution was prepared and 2 ml was pipetted out in to a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with the diluent, and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of the drug under UV exposure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selection of Analytical Wavelength

The UV spectrum of the drug (10 µg/ml) in the selected diluent (mobile phase) was scanned from 200-400 nm against the diluent blank. A distinct maximum at 259 nm with no diluent interference was observed, therefore 259 nm was fixed as the analytical wavelength. The UV spectrum shown in (Fig 2).

FIGURE 2: UV spectrum of Inosine Pranobex by using diluent at 259 nm

Method development

To develop a HPLC method for estimating the Inosine Pranobex, the chromatographic conditions were

optimized to produce the chromatogram with lesser analysis time. Several trials have been conducted to develop the optimized method for Inosine Pranobex estimation. Various mobile phase combinations like Water: acetonitrile: methanol (40:30:30 % v/v/v) with flow rate 1.00 ml/min (low retention time and peak shape not good), Water: acetonitrile: methanol + 0.1 % formic acid (40:30:30 % v/v/v) with flow rate 0.7 ml/min

(Peak splitting was observed), Water: acetonitrile: methanol (60:15:25 % v/v/v) with flow rate 1.00 ml/min (retention time and peak shape not good), Water: acetonitrile: methanol (60:15:25 % v/v/v) with flow rate 0.7 ml/min (peak shape not good), Water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 % v/v/v) with flow rate 1.00 ml/min (low retention time) and Water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 % v/v/v) with flow rate 0.7 ml/min has shown symmetrical peaks with excellent satisfactory retention time. Based on the chemical nature of Inosine Pranobex, the developmental trials were performed. During method optimization, the column was selected based on retention time, tailing factor, no. of theoretical plates, and shape of the peak. The mobile phase's selection was done based on the polarity of the functional groups contained in Inosine Pranobex. By considering all these aspects, the separation was carried out using Shimadzu C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.6 mm × 5 μm) with the mobile phase containing Water: acetonitrile: methanol (80:10:10 % v/v/v) with flow rate 0.7 ml/minute. 20 μL was the injection volume and the effluents from the column were detected at 259 nm. using UV detector. Inosine Pranobex was eluted at a retention time of 2.8 minutes. The optimized conditions and chromatograms for blank and standard of Inosine Pranobex are given in Table 3 and Figures 3–4.

FIGURE 3: Chromatogram for Blank

FIGURE 4: Optimized chromatogram for Standard

Method validation

System suitability

Standard Inosine Pranobex solution was injected six times, and their corresponding chromatograms were obtained. The theoretical plate count exceeded 2,000, the USP tailing was under 2, and the percent RSD was under 2 %, according to observations. All of the requirements for system suitability were met and fall within acceptable ranges. The data given as (Table 3)

TABLE 3: System suitability parameter of Inosine Pranobex chromatogram

PARAMETER	LIMIT	RESULT
Peak area	-	2596517
Number of theoretical plate or efficacy	>2000	2,028
Tailing factor	<2	0.734
Retention time	-	2.8 mins

Linearity and calibration curve

Five different concentrations ranging from 20 to 100 μg/ml were prepared and linearity was estimated in a duplicate manner. The linearity equation for Inosine Pranobex was $y = 65426x + 7927.3$. For the estimated drug, the observed correlation coefficient was 0.9999. For the calibration curve over the concentration range, the data have shown a good correlation. Thus, it was discovered that the current method was linear. The data are shown in Table 4 and results are provided in Figure 5.

Table 4: Linearity Data For Inosine Pranobex

CONCENTRATION	AREA
20	1340295
40	2599516
60	3953707
80	5222061
100	6559705

Figure 5: Calibration Curve For Inosine Pranobex**Table 5: Precision Data For Inosine Pranobex**

SI. NO	AREA	AMOUNT FOUND (mg/tab)	% PURITY	S. D	% RSD
1	2596517	497.58	99.51	0.1011	0.1047
2	2599600	498.20	99.64		
3	2599699	498.20	99.64		
4	2598602	498.70	99.74		
5	2599670	498.90	99.78		
6	2599520	498.09	99.61		
Average % Purity =			99.65		

FIGURE 6: Chromatogram for sample

Precision

Six injections from a sample solution (40 µg/ml) were provided for system precision, and the regions were noted. Calculations were made for the average percentage purity, standard deviation, and % RSD. The % RSD for Inosine Pranobex was 0.10 %. As per the limit of precision, the system precision was acceptable. The result values for system precision were provided in Table 5 and chromatogram are shown in Figure 6.

Accuracy

Three levels of accuracy samples were created using the usual addition method. Three doses were given at each level, and the mean % recovery was calculated. Inosine Pranobex recovery rate was observed within the acceptable ranges when evaluating the accuracy of the current suggested method discussed in this section. The results were provided in Table 6.

TABLE 6: Accuracy Data For Inosine Pranobex

Conc %	Amount Present	Amount Added	Amount Estimated	Amount Recovery	Average % Recovery	S. D	% RSD
50 %	40	20	60.30	20.30	101.50	0.0288	0.0284
100 %	40	20	79.87	39.87	99.67	0.1527	0.1532
150 %	40	20	100.03	60.03	100.05	0.0896	0.0895

n – mean of 3 observations

LOD AND LOQ:

To calculate the average of standard deviation of absorbance, and “S” is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve. The data were provided in Table 7.

TABLE 7: Optical Characteristics Data For Inosine Pranobex

Parameter	RP-HPLC for Inosine Pranobex
Regression equation (y=mx +c)	y= 65426x+7927,3
Slope (m)	65426
Intercept (c)	7927.3
S.E of intercept	16858.19
S. D	41293.96
LOD (µg/ml)	2.0828
LOQ (µg/ml)	6.3115

Ruggedness:

The ruggedness of the method was confirmed by performing the analysis under different conditions,

and the % RSD was found to be within acceptable limits, indicating good reproducibility. The result was shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Ruggedness Data for Inosine Pranobex

Parameter	Average % Purity	S. D	% Rsd
Analyst-1	99.31	0.0264	0.0266
Analyst-2	99.35	0.1105	0.1108
Instrument-1	99.31	0.0152	0.0153
Instrument-2	99.99	0.1913	0.1914

n – mean of 3 observations

Robustness

Some of the chromatographic conditions were altered, and the percent RSD values were calculated to determine the robustness. The conditions are wavelength minus (258 nm) and wavelength plus (260 nm), flow rate minus (0.6 ml/minute) and flow rate

plus (0.8 ml/minute), mobile phase plus and minus (79:11:11 %v/v/v) and mobile phase plus and minus (81:9:11 %v/v/v). The percent RSD values are within the limits, and the system suitability parameters were not significantly impacted. Hence the method was said to be robust. The data for robustness is given the Table 9.

Table 9: Robustness Data For Inosine Pranobex

Parameter	Amount Found	% Purity	Sd	% Rsd
Flow Rate				
0.6 MI/Min	497.25	99.45	0.1401	0.1408
0.7 MI/Min	496.61	99.32	0.1550	0.1560
0.8 MI/Min	496.68	99.33	0.0351	0.0353
Wavelength				
258 Nm	498.77	99.75	0.2909	0.2916
259 Nm	496.42	99.28	0.0404	0.0407
260 Nm	499.63	99.92	0.0115	0.0115
Mobile Phase				
Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (78:11:11 %v/v/v)	500.79	100.15	0.0896	0.0894
Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (80:10:10 %v/v/v)	496.23	99.24	0.0115	0.0116
Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (81:9:10 %v/v/v)	498.88	99.77	0.3724	0.3732

n= mean of 3 observations

Stability-indicating studies

These studies are carried out to assess the stability of the drug under defined stress conditions. Studies are performed under the stress condition like acid, base, oxidative, reduction, hydrolysis, photolytic, thermal and UV degradation. The Inosine Pranobex standard

was used in degradation experiments, and the stress induced standard solution were injected. All results obtained from the assay of the injected materials are within no significant of degradation, however, no extra small peak has been appeared in degradation studies. Studies on stress degradation's findings were presented in Table 10 and the chromatograms were provided in Figures 7–14.

Table 10: Degradation Data For Inosine Pranobex

Stress conditions	Typical conditions	Time interval	Degradation results
Acid degradation	0.1N H ₂ SO ₄	24hrs	Not degraded
Base degradation	0.1 N KOH	24hrs	Not degraded
Hydrolytic degradation	HPLC grade water	24hrs	Not degraded
Oxidative degradation	0.3 % H ₂ O ₂	24hrs	Not degraded
Photolytic degradation	Sunlight	04hrs	Not degraded
Reduction degradation	10 % Sodium bisulfate	24hrs	Not degraded
Thermal degradation	70°C	24hrs	Not degraded
UV – degradation	UV- light	24hrs	Not degraded

Figure: 7 Acid Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 8 Base Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 9 Oxidative Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 12 Photolytic Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 10 Hydrolytic Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 13 Thermal Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 11 Reduction Degradation Chromatogram Of Inosine Pranobex

Figure: 14 Uv Light Degradation Chromatogram of Inosine Pranobex

Table 12: Key Advantage of the Developed Stability indicating RP-HPLC Method for Inosine Pranobex

PARAMETER	ADVANTAGE
Novelty	First RP-HPLC method developed using this specific mobile phase ratio for Inosine Pranobex- a novel contribution to literature
Linearity(R^2)	Excellent correlation coefficient of 0.9999, indicating high linearity
Mobile phase composition	Water: Methanol: Acetonitrile (80:10:10 %v/v/v)- simple, economical and reproducible
Diluent	Same as mobile phase ensures compatibility and minimizes solvent effects
Specificity	No interference from excipients; sharp, well -resolved peak obtained

Stability advantage	No degradation observed under stress conditions (acidic, alkaline, hydrolytic, reduction, thermal, oxidation photolytic and UV) confirming the drug stability
Accuracy & precision	High recovery values and low % RSD confirming method reliability
Cost – effectiveness	Utilizes readily available solvents (water, methanol, acetonitrile) without buffer requirement
Eco- friendly aspect	Buffer – free system reduces salt waste; high proportion of water in the mobile phase lowers organic solvent use, making the method greener and safer
Industrial applicability	Simple, reproducible, and validated method suitable for routine quality control, bulk analysis and large-scale industrial applications

CONCLUSION

A stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the quantification of Inosine Pranobex in both bulk and tablet dosage form. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Shimadzu C₁₈ column (4.5 × 250 mm × 5 μm) using a mobile phase with a high proportion of water, acetonitrile, and methanol in the ratio of 80:10:10 %v/v/v at a flow rate of 0.7 ml/min, with UV detection at 259 nm. The method demonstrated excellent specificity, with no detectable degradation of Inosine Pranobex under various forced degradation conditions—including acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reduction, hydrolysis, thermal, photolysis and UV stress- confirming its stability-indicating capability.

This method offers multiple advantages, including simplicity and rapid analysis time, which facilitates high sample throughput suitable for routine quality control. The high aqueous content in the mobile phase, combined with the absence of buffer, reduces system maintenance and prolongs column life, while also minimizing environmental impact and operational costs. The procedure exhibits high sensitivity, precision, and accuracy with minimal sample preparation, thereby reducing sample loss and analytical variability. Moreover, the method is robust and reproducible across deliberate variations in chromatographic conditions, ensuring reliable performance. These attributes make the validated RP-HPLC method well-suited for stability studies, regulatory compliance, and routine assay of Inosine Pranobex in pharmaceutical formulations.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTRESTS

Declared none.

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